

Pedagogical Practices and Translanguaging: English Language Teachers' Experiences in Nepal's Multilingual Classrooms

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Abstract: This phenomenological study examines English language teachers' real-world experiences negotiating the challenges of multilingual classrooms in Nepal (García & Wei, 2014). In order to address the difficulties of linguistic diversity and promote inclusivity, the research explores how teachers adapt their pedagogical practices, drawing on the stories of four teachers who work in various linguistic and cultural contexts (Cummins, 2000). Using the translanguaging theoretical framework, the study shows how teachers make use of their students' linguistic assets to improve identity affirmation, engagement, and comprehension (García, 2009; García & Lin, 2017). The findings highlight the transformative potential of translanguaging pedagogy by revealing themes like navigating language barriers, adapting to a multilingual classroom, and emotional and social challenges (García & Kleyn, 2019). The study offers important new information on teaching English in multicultural contexts and emphasises the necessity of context-sensitive teacher training to promote multilingual education

(Kumaravadivelu, 2020; Phyak & Sharma, 2018).

Keywords: *translanguaging; multilingual classrooms; English language teaching; Nepal; pedagogical practices; linguistic diversity; teacher experiences*

Introduction

This phenomenological study aims to investigate the lived experiences of English language teachers in Nepali multilingual classrooms, with an emphasis on how they view, understand, and deal with linguistic diversity in the classroom (Creswell & Poth, 2016). In my more than ten years of teaching English in different schools, I have overcome many obstacles and achieved many successes. It took blood, sweat, and tears to accomplish this, but my love of teaching has motivated me to keep learning new things in order to improve my teaching techniques and have a significant influence (Farrell, 2015). I have struggled with issues like how to inspire and involve students in the language classroom throughout my teaching career (Dörnyei & Ushioda, 2011). How can I ensure inclusivity in my classroom? Am I fairly evaluating my students' language skills? How can I make my English language instruction engaging, useful, and long-lasting? My professional development has been influenced by my curiosity about these issues (Richards & Farrell, 2005). I've learnt about topics like classroom management, child psychology, and

teaching techniques from a few teacher training sessions (Freeman & Johnson, 1998). However, because I had previously taught in schools that used English as a Medium of Instruction (EMI) with students primarily from Nepali-speaking backgrounds, "English now increasingly serves as 'a medium of instruction' in growing number of schools and particularly in universities worldwide" (Dearden, 2015, p. 12). I hardly ever heard conversations about teaching in multilingual classrooms (García & Wei, 2014). My teaching environment has recently changed to a public school with students from a variety of linguistic backgrounds. I now face a different set of difficulties as a result of this, I have to rely a lot on Nepali translations when implementing EMI in this setting, and I frequently have to deal with cultural differences that I was not previously aware of (Phyak, 2013). In order to capture the essence of English language teachers' experiences and advance knowledge of inclusive and successful teaching methods, this study aims to explore challenges, techniques, and perspectives of these teachers in Nepali multilingual classrooms (García & Lin, 2017).

Classrooms in today's education systems are growing more multilingual and multicultural, reflecting broader societal changes brought about by globalization, migration, and various demographic changes (Banks, 2015). This diversity can create complex teaching environments where traditional, one-size-fits-all instructional approaches often fall short (Banks, 2015; García, 2009). "The majority of classes in Nepal consist of linguistic and cultural diversity where students need to have different learning materials, methodologies and learning styles which help them minimize the problems of interaction and comprehension" (Bhandari, 2016, p. 45). This poses distinct problems and opportunities for teachers, particularly English language teachers, who have to adapt their educational techniques to their students' different requirements (Cummins, 2000; García & Wei, 2014). The European Commission's (2015) report *Language Teaching and Learning in the Multilingual Classrooms* identifies "multilingual classroom" as a "challenge," which is actually meant as a "problem" (p. 23).

The presence of students from multiple cultural backgrounds and languages is a defining feature of multilingual classrooms. According to García (2009), "a multilingual classroom is one in which students contribute their linguistic accumulation to the learning process and translanguaging techniques are employed to make the most of these varied linguistic resources for communication and education" (p. 142). It could be challenging to treat students from diverse linguistic backgrounds as students' understanding, background information, learning capacities, and cognitive capabilities may vary, and there can be issues with vocabulary learning, pronunciation, comprehending and overall language acquisition (Cummins, 2000; García & Lin, 2017). Tin (2014) states that since both English and English language teaching (ELT) have become widely available throughout the world, there has been a greater focus on social context and the need to comprehend how English is studied and taught in various contexts (p. 78). In order to effectively teach English to students from diverse origins, educators must adjust their techniques (Kumaravadivelu, 2020). Students' accomplishments can be improved with the use of appropriate teaching strategies, which will ultimately affect their ability to grasp the English language (Dautbašić & Saračević, 2019).

Multilingual pedagogy and translanguaging have grown in importance in English language instruction, especially in linguistically diverse contexts like Nepal (García & Kleyn, 2019; Phyak & Sharma, 2018). Translanguaging is an effective tool that allows students to use their entire linguistic repertoire, improving comprehension and identity affirmation, according to García and Kleyn (2019). This method promotes inclusivity and engagement in the classroom by validating students' native languages while simultaneously strengthening their command of English (García, 2009; García & Wei, 2014). This perspective is supported by Yadav (2021) and García (2014),

who point out that translanguaging enables teachers to lessen cognitive load by elucidating complex concepts in multiple languages, thereby improving accessibility for multilingual students.

In multilingual classrooms, the relationship between language, identity, and education is essential (Norton, 2013). De Costa and Norton (2017) stress that in order to foster an empowering learning environment, it is important to recognise students' linguistic identities. García (2014) shares this opinion, arguing that translanguaging affirms students' cultural and linguistic identities while also improving academic performance. Recognising and validating students' native languages is crucial for their social and emotional health, creating a sense of community, and enhancing learning outcomes in Nepal's diverse classrooms (Cummins, 2000; García & Lin, 2017).

Since English-medium instruction (EMI) is widely used in Nepali schools, multilingualism poses special challenges for teachers (Phyak & Sharma, 2018). To address the varied needs of students from different linguistic backgrounds, teachers frequently need to adapt their pedagogical approaches, according to Giri (2010) and Phyak and Sharma (2018). In multilingual classrooms, teachers need to be creative and frequently use strategies like code-switching and visual aids to help students understand (García & Wei, 2014). According to Kumaravadivelu (2020), these adaptations are in line with his macrostrategies for teaching languages, which stress the importance of flexible and context-sensitive methods.

Phyak (2013) critiques Nepal's multilingual education policies, highlighting the conflict between the early use of indigenous languages and the later predominance of English. Because students' levels of English proficiency vary greatly, this presents difficulties for both teachers and students (Giri, 2010). The educational system's preference for English over native tongues has pedagogical implications especially in rural regions where various linguistic communities live side by side (Phyak & Sharma, 2018). In order to close the gap between students' native tongues and English and to foster a more welcoming and productive learning environment, translanguaging becomes an essential tool in multilingual settings (García & Lin, 2017).

Despite an increasing emphasis on multilingual education, little research has been done to document teachers' real-world experiences navigating linguistic diversity, which leaves a gap in our knowledge of the usefulness of multilingual pedagogical approaches (García & Wei, 2014). There is a need for significant research into the reliable approaches and practices that these teachers use to address linguistic diversity (Cummins, 2000). Although a lot of research has been done on the effectiveness of multilingual education, García and Wei (2014) contend that little attention has been paid to the real-world experiences of teachers who are leading the charge in putting these practices into practice. There is a knowledge gap regarding how teachers view and handle the challenges of multilingual classrooms because the majority of research focusses on student outcomes (García & Lin, 2017). According to García and Lin (2017), researching how teachers behave in multilingual classrooms can reveal important information about effective instructional strategies and the difficulties in putting inclusive education into practice. Especially in under-represented contexts like Nepal, this research can add to this expanding body of knowledge (Phyak, 2013; Shah, 2020).

Theoretical Framework

To frame my study, I have used the translanguaging theoretical framework. This theory is developed by Ofelia García in 2009 (García, 2009). I am astonished knowing how frequently translanguaging is defined as flexible, live, inclusive student centered language teaching

approach that addresses and utilizes the linguistic skills of multilingual students (García & Kleyn, 2019). It is such practice that captures the real, authentic, day to day approach in which students interact, make sense and connect them across language (García & Wei, 2014). Using this frame in the research, it aims to understand how English teachers use it to negotiate with students' varied linguistic resources that could support learning and how such practices inspire their own teaching experiences (García & Lin, 2017). By exposing these real-life practices, the study hopefully aims to bridge the gap between theoretical debate practical implications of translanguaging in multilingual classrooms of English Medium instruction (EMI) settings (Phyak & Sharma, 2018).

Translanguaging views multilingual is a dynamic process where students and teachers use different language they know to communicate and create meaningful learning (García, 2009). García and Lin (2017) highlight that translanguaging make the classroom more inclusive place for each student encouraging them to engage deeply on what they are learning and validating their linguistic identities. Furthermore they argue that to promote truly an inclusive and successful teaching strategies, it requires to have the understanding of specific context in which translanguaging comes into practice (García & Lin, 2017). This viewpoint resonates with what I have observed in multilingual classrooms, where language confines frequently integrate together (Personal reflection supported by García & Wei, 2014).

García and Wei (2014) view translanguaging as an exercise where multilingual speakers utilize their whole linguistic repertoire encompassing both their mother tongue or first language and second language to accomplish communicative goals. Translanguaging ensures the flexibility of bilingual speakers to select and blend language features from other languages to fulfill their communicative needs (García & Wei, 2014). This involves, using vocabulary, grammar and also non-standard use of language from other parts of their linguistic repertoire (García, 2009). Translanguaging is not just switching between languages but also utilizing all the linguistic resources to effectively and successfully exchange meaning and achieve communicative goals (García & Kleyn, 2019). García and Wei (2014) also emphasize the potential benefits of translanguaging in education. They argue that translanguaging empowers learners by validating their native language and their cultural identities. It also enhances cognitive development as it facilitates deeper understanding (García & Wei, 2014). It challenges monolingual norms and creates translanguaging spaces to promote social justice and equity (García & Lin, 2017).

Lev Vygotsky's (1978) Sociocultural theory also complements on translanguaging suggesting that learning takes place best through social interaction and for this language plays the key role for thinking and understanding (Vygotsky, 1978). If students are allowed to speak all their language, that can help them grasp and understand the new ideas effectively (García, 2009). This sociocultural theory also supports on using all the possible linguistic knowledge or resources to students because these are significant to value their cultural identities and language learning process (Vygotsky, 1978; García & Wei, 2014). This view closely aligns with the view of translanguaging by providing the learners the opportunities to draw on their all linguistic knowledge by allowing multiple language to coexist in their classroom to make meaningful learning and offers an opportunity to recognize students' native language not as challenges but it is assets during language learning (García & Lin, 2017).

Similarly, Hornberger's (2003) Continua of Biliteracy framework also aid on the view of translanguaging that language learning and literacy development is perplexing, adaptable, dynamic and influenced by various factors like culture and context (Hornberger, 2003). It throws light on how reading and writing can be learned in more than one language by figuring out

different factors like learners' experiences, social background, the way how languages are used (Hornberger, 2003). It believes on the educational practices that is built upon students' own linguistic repertoire encouraging them to combinedly use their each language skills rather than using them separately (Hornberger, 2003). Therefore Hornberger's Continua of Biliteracy framework supports on implementing translanguaging approach in diverse teaching and learning environments (García & Lin, 2017).

Nepal Context and Previous Studies

Different studies done in Nepal are the proof of challenges and opportunities of implementing translanguaging in linguistically diverse classrooms (Phyak, 2013; Giri, 2010; Shah, 2020). Giri (2010) has investigated that Nepal's education system is prevalently influenced by English because the widely used English-medium instruction (EMI) has marginalized the local languages. However teachers want to use home language to scaffold students' comprehension, they are bound with institutional regulation of not using any other languages except English as a medium of instruction (Giri, 2010). Despite of all these some teachers couldn't stop themselves incorporating students home language informally to enhance meaningful learning and rapport building (Phyak, 2013).

An ethnographic study by Phyak (2013) investigates that there is disparity between Nepal's policy on language in education and real classroom practices. He finds out that though, it is clearly mentioned in the policies for multilingual instruction classrooms are dominated by English (Phyak, 2013). It is so unjustifiable to students because they are struggling to develop the concept on what they are learning just because of the language used for instruction (Phyak & Sharma, 2018). However teachers are frequently reliable on translanguaging to facilitate the learners to clarify the complex concepts as well as to incorporate their cultural identities with learning activities (Phyak, 2013).

Lama (2022) in his research explores that teachers are putting more effort on crating translingual spaces in their classrooms. She reveals that teachers are much concern about their linguistically and culturally diverse students, therefore they are very consciously drawing on resources from their multilingual students so they could create an inclusive along with participatory learning environment (Lama, 2022). These teachers are daring to challenge the dominant ideologies through integrating multiple language for instruction, relation building and to support their socio-emotional support (Lama, 2022).

Promod K. Shah in is studies like (Shah, 2020; Shah & Li, 2020), has explored that language ideologies and education policy goes against teachers' practice of translanguaging in their classroom. His study has documented how teachers deal with the power dynamic, schools' regulations and parents' expectations to create spaces for their students to respect and validate their linguistic identities (Shah, 2020; Shah & Li, 2020). Shah suggests the necessity of language awareness and clarity on language ideology while implementing translanguaging approach (Shah, 2020).

These studies clarify that translanguaging is not formally accepted and approved however it is widely practiced by many teachers as this approach is pragmatically and pedagogically sound in response to Nepal's multilingual classrooms (García & Lin, 2017; Phyak, 2013; Shah, 2020).

Policy Context

Nepal's educational policy has also officially recognized and prioritized linguistic diversity but unfortunately it fails to implement it effectively (Phyak & Sharma, 2018). The Nepal's Constitution (2015) and Nepal Education Policy (2019) have given emphasis for mother-tongue

instruction as it is mentioned in the Constitution of Nepal (2015) that every community has right to get education in their mother tongue (Government of Nepal, 2015). Similarly, the National Education Policy (2019) emphasizes that early grade instruction in students' mother tongue is the key strategy to improve learning outcomes (Ministry of Education, Science and Technology, 2019). So these policies are supporting multilingual education to promote inclusive and equitable education (Phyak, 2013; Giri, 2010).

Besides these policies, The School Sector Development Plan (SSDP) (2016-2023) has also supported mother tongue based multilingual education in early grades that is ECD to grade 3, to support students for better learning through their own language (Ministry of Education, 2016). Many municipalities have also developed their own Local Curriculum Frameworks to meet their local needs and also include local languages in teaching (Phyak & Sharma, 2018).

Hence, translanguaging is pedagogically strong and appropriate contextually in multilingual classroom (García & Lin, 2017). But it should be implemented effectively by bridging the gap between policy and practice (Shah, 2020; Shah & Li, 2020).

Methodology

This study had used a qualitative phenomenological approach to investigate the lived experiences of English language teachers negotiating the challenges of multilingual classrooms in Nepal (Creswell & Poth, 2016).

Four English language teachers from diverse linguistic and cultural contexts participated in this study (Patton, 2015). Mrs. Dulal, from a renowned private school in Bhaktapur, primarily teaches Nepali-speaking students. Mrs. Yadav, from a public school in Dang, works in a setting where Tharu, Maithili and Nepali are the dominant languages. Mrs. Gurung, a teacher from a public school in Chitwan area, teaches in a community where Gurung and Chepang languages are prevalent. Mrs. Lama, from a private school in Kathmandu, manages a linguistically diverse classroom with students speaking Newar, Tamang, Nepali and other languages.

Data was collected through semi-structured interviews, field notes, audio and video (Creswell & Poth, 2016). Thematic analysis was used to identify recurring patterns and themes, connecting them with the theoretical framework of translanguaging (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Ethical considerations were maintained, with participants providing informed consent and respecting cultural sensitivities (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016). The research aims to understand how teachers adapt their practices in multilingual classrooms to accommodate linguistic and cultural diversity guided by the research question: How do English language teachers adapt their teaching strategies to accommodate linguistic diversity in Nepali multilingual classrooms?

Teachers' Adaptation to Multilingual Classrooms

English language teachers face both distinctive opportunities and difficulties in multilingual classrooms, where they have to adapt their teaching strategies to accommodate students from linguistically and culturally diverse backgrounds (García & Wei, 2014; Cummins, 2000). The four teacher participants' narratives demonstrate the variety of strategies they use, which reflects the sophisticated dynamics of teaching in multilingual environments (García & Lin, 2017).

According to a teacher at a private school in Kathmandu, although the majority of the students in their class spoke Nepali, Newar and Tamang were occasionally used. She acknowledged, *"I rely on translation because I often feel that my training hasn't prepared me to use students' linguistic resources effectively. Using visual aids, gestures, and pictures also help me make lessons clear"* (Personal interview, 2024). According to García (2009), good teacher training enable teachers to

smoothly incorporate all of their students' language resources, creating a multilingual environment in the classroom. Although this teacher primarily used English for formal instruction, demonstrating little interest in the subject, she used Nepali in class discussions to clarify abstract English concepts, they primarily used English for formal instruction and showed little interest in their students' other native tongues (García & Wei, 2014). Their experience highlights the difficulties implicit multilingualism (Brutt-Griffler, 2017) presents in classrooms where teachers lack fluency in the native tongues of their students.

A public school teacher in Dang said that the students in their class were from a variety of linguistic backgrounds, including Tharu, Nepali, and Maithali. She clarified, saying, *"At first, I thought it was overwhelming, but I've come to realise that letting students use their native languages in group projects really helps. In order for students to support one another, I divide them into small groups based on a shared language"* (Personal interview, 2024). The use of students' linguistic repertoires as learning resources is in line with García's (2014) translanguaging theory which emphasizes translanguaging as an effective teaching technique that allows students to use all of their language resources to comprehend difficult ideas, communicate them, and engage in the learning process. It facilitates the inclusion and acceptance of students' cultural and linguistic identities in the classroom (García & Lin, 2017). *"Seeing students use their native tongues to explain concepts to their peers is endearing,"* the teacher continued. It encourages cooperation and diversity (Personal interview, 2024).

One teacher from Bhaktapur, Mrs. Dulal, talked about her experiences working with students who spoke Nepali and Newar. Although the majority of students feel at ease speaking Nepali, she clarified, *"I often encourage them to share their ideas in their mother tongue as well, however they rarely use it. They feel more self-assured and rooted as a result. I was not trained"* (Personal interview, 2024). Untrained teachers frequently find it difficult to successfully address language barriers (Ball, 2011), *"in translanguaging, but when I see the advantages for my students, it comes easily to me in the classroom. It's difficult to balance linguistic and cultural diversity, but it also adds meaning to my teaching,"* she continued (Personal interview, 2024).

In a classroom full of Chepang and Gurung speakers, a teacher from Chitwan stressed the value of cultural relevance in their teachings (García & Lin, 2017). He stated, *"In order to introduce new vocabulary and concepts in English, I integrate stories and experiences from my students' cultural backgrounds." "But occasionally, my inability to communicate effectively in Chepang restricts how much I can relate to them"* (Personal interview, 2024). Given that García and Lin (2017) support instructional strategies that honour students' cultural identities, their method emphasises the importance of incorporating cultural context into language instruction.

Together, these stories show how teachers use strategies like translanguaging, cultural inclusion, and visual aids to meet the demands of multilingual classrooms (García & Kleyn, 2019). Their methods, however, frequently result from independent work rather than formal education, indicating a lack of opportunities for professional growth (Farrell, 2015). In order to validate students' linguistic and cultural identities, inclusive pedagogical frameworks are essential, as highlighted by García (2014) and García and Lin (2017). These accounts demonstrate the necessity of specialised teacher training programs and systemic support in order to enable teachers to successfully negotiate the challenges of multilingual classrooms (Richards & Farrell, 2005).

Navigating Language Barriers with Translanguaging

Language barriers frequently present serious obstacles to efficient teaching and learning in multilingual classrooms (Cummins, 2000). Language barriers frequently make it difficult for students to understand and participate in class when the medium of instruction is different from their native tongues (Cummins, 2000; García & Wei, 2014). Nonetheless, translanguaging provides teachers with an effective tool to close these gaps and establish a welcoming classroom (García & Lin, 2017). Canagarajah (2011), highlights translanguaging as a valuable tool for teachers to manage linguistic diversity in multilingual classrooms, promoting collaborative meaning-making and active student participation.

Mrs Lama:

"I encourage the students to use their native languages during group discussions or while brainstorming ideas. In the beginning they were little hesitant because not all the students understand each of their languages but later gradually they started feeling comfortable. This has not only enriched our classroom interactions but also given students the confidence to articulate their thoughts in English later." (Personal interview, 2024)

Mrs Yadav:

"It is not easy to teach in a classroom full of Tharu and Maithali speakers. I frequently explain important terms and concepts in both Nepali and their native tongues. When teaching new vocabulary, for example, I first explain the word in Nepali, then I relate it to their native tongue before translating it into English. They will be able to associate the new word with something they already know." (Personal interview, 2024)

Mrs Dulal:

"Initially, I struggled to explain abstract concepts in English to my students. Now, I encourage students to discuss these topics in Newari, Tamang or Nepali, whichever they are comfortable with, before presenting their ideas in English. This not only boosts their confidence but also ensures they understand the material thoroughly." (Personal interview, 2024)

Mr. Gurung:

"The majority of my students speak Gurung or Chepang at home. They initially felt intimidated by English and were hesitant to speak in class. I first gave them permission to express themselves in their mother tongue. Together, we gradually translated their ideas into English. They now take part more actively and are less hesitant to make mistakes." (Personal interview, 2024)

These teachers' experiences and perceptions show how effective translanguaging is as a teaching strategy for overcoming language barriers (García & Kleyn, 2019). Teachers like Mrs. Lama, Mrs. Yadav, Mrs. Dulal, and Mr. Gurung embody García's (2014) vision of inclusive education, where linguistic diversity is celebrated and all students are empowered to learn and thrive, by incorporating translanguaging strategies (García & Lin, 2017).

Emotional and Social Experiences in Multilingual Classrooms

For both teachers and students, multilingual classrooms are places of complex emotional and social experiences in addition to academic learning (Cummins, 2000; García & Wei, 2014). Bhandari and Dhakal (2022) explored that teachers can foster a more peaceful and encouraging environment by implementing inclusive practices and culturally sensitive teaching strategies. Addressing these dynamics needs empathy, flexibility, and an in-depth understanding of the linguistic and cultural identities of their students on the part of English language teachers (García & Lin, 2017). According to researchers like Cummins (2000) and García (2014), establishing

inclusive and equitable learning environments in multilingual classrooms requires promoting positive emotional and social experiences. While social inclusion fosters cooperation and respect among diverse learners, emotional engagement is strongly associated with students' academic achievement and general well-being (Dörnyei & Ushioda, 2011). Neupane (2024) investigated how students' motivation and language proficiency were improved by incorporating social emotional learning strategies like encouraging self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship skills, and responsible decision-making.

"Many of my students are hesitant to speak in English because they fear making mistakes," Mrs. Dulal said in response to the emotional difficulties her students encounter (Personal interview, 2024). *"I let them express themselves in Nepali or Newari first in an effort to foster a supportive environment. They become more willing to participate when they witness me and their peers appreciating their efforts."* (Personal interview, 2024). Her method supports Cummins' (2000) view that emotional security, which is critical for learning, is fostered by affirming students' cultural and linguistic identities. Mrs. Dulal helps her students overcome their anxiety and create a sense of community in the classroom by encouraging them to speak in their native tongues (García & Wei, 2014).

"Even though the majority of my students speak Nepali, they frequently feel alone because they struggle with English," Mrs. Lama said, offering insights into the emotional experiences of students in a more urban and diverse setting (Personal interview, 2024). *"I make sure they get the chance to participate in peer discussions in their native tongues. They feel seen and valued when I also recognise their efforts in class."* (Personal interview, 2024). Her approach supports Cummins' (2000) claim that students' emotional and social experiences are greatly influenced by teachers' encouragement and acknowledgement. Mrs. Lama makes sure that no student feels excluded by fostering a culture in the classroom that values all opinions (García & Lin, 2017).

Mrs. Yadav, who made a similar observation about her students said, *"Many Tharu and Maithali speaking students in my class feel excluded during group activities because they cannot fully express themselves in English. I advise them to create multilingual groups so they can express themselves in Maithili, Tharu, and Nepali. As a result, they now feel more included and have formed friendships."* (Personal interview, 2024). This approach supports García's (2014) assertion that multilingual classrooms should be places where students' linguistic resources are viewed as strengths rather than weaknesses. Mrs. Yadav encourages inclusivity and teamwork by promoting social interactions across linguistic boundaries, both of which are essential for students' social and emotional growth (García & Kleyn, 2019).

"Some of my students feel ashamed to speak their native language in class because they think it's inferior to Nepali or English," Mr. Gurung said, highlighting the cultural difficulties his students face (Personal interview, 2024). *"By asking them to share traditional tales or songs, I make it a point to honour their languages and cultures. Now they have been able to connect with their peers and take pride in their heritage."* (Personal interview, 2024). His approach supports Canagarajah's (2011) argument that social cohesion and emotional resilience are enhanced when students' linguistic and cultural identities are valued. Mr. Gurung encourages his students to embrace their identities while also enhancing classroom interactions by incorporating cultural practices into his teaching (García & Lin, 2017).

Linguistic and cultural dynamics have a profound connection to social and emotional experiences in multilingual classrooms (Norton, 2013). These teachers use techniques that support social inclusion, emotional stability, and identity affirmation for their pupils (García & Wei, 2014). These practices are supported by academics like García (2014) and Canagarajah

(2011), who stress that multilingual classrooms should be places where students feel appreciated, respected, and connected in addition to being places of academic learning. Teachers can design inclusive and transformative classrooms by addressing the emotional and social aspects of multilingual education (García & Lin, 2017).

Findings and Discussions

The findings of the research highlight the variety of opportunities and difficulties faced by English language teachers in multilingual classrooms (García & Wei, 2014; Cummins, 2000). Three major themes emerge from the analysis of the participant narratives and their alignment with academic viewpoints: Teachers' Adaptation to Multilingual Classrooms, Emotional and Social Experiences in Multilingual Classrooms, and Navigating Language Barriers with Translanguaging (García & Lin, 2017). In multilingual settings, these themes offer a nuanced understanding of how educators respond to linguistic diversity, modify their pedagogical approaches, and establish emotionally supportive environments (Creswell & Poth, 2016).

The study emphasises the necessity of professional development programs that give teachers the tools they need to successfully manage multilingual classrooms (Richards & Farrell, 2005; Farrell, 2015). Teachers can turn multilingual classrooms into welcoming environments where all students can succeed by embracing translanguaging, encouraging emotional connections, and making adjustments for various kinds of needs (García & Kleyn, 2019; García & Lin, 2017).

Conclusion

This study examined the lived experiences of English language instructors in Nepali multilingual classrooms with a focus on three main themes; teachers' adaptation to multilingual classrooms, overcoming language barriers through translanguaging, and emotional and social experiences in multilingual classrooms (García & Wei, 2014; Cummins, 2000). Through the accounts of four teacher participants from various geographical areas: Kathmandu, Bhaktapur, Chitwan, and Dang, the study demonstrated the difficulties of teaching in these kinds of settings and the methods teachers use to get past obstacles and create a welcoming, encouraging learning environment (Creswell & Poth, 2016).

The findings highlight the value of translanguaging as a crucial teaching strategy in multilingual environments (García & Kleyn, 2019; García & Lin, 2017). Teachers not only improve comprehension but also validate students' cultural identities by letting them use their entire linguistic repertoire (García, 2009; García & Wei, 2014). Furthermore, in order to create fair and stimulating learning environments, teachers must adjust to the multilingual nature of their classrooms (Cummins, 2000). Furthermore, it was discovered that students' emotional and social experiences were crucial to their overall learning journey (Dörnyei & Ushioda, 2011). Students gain confidence and a sense of belonging when their teachers celebrate cultural diversity, validate their native tongues, and offer emotional support (García & Lin, 2017).

In conclusion this study highlights the transformative potential of multilingual classrooms when teachers prioritise students' emotional well-being and adopt diverse teaching strategies, such as translanguaging (García & Kleyn, 2019). Professional development programs must focus on giving teachers the skills and information they need to successfully handle the challenges of multilingual classrooms in order to support them even more (Richards & Farrell, 2005; Farrell, 2015). By doing this, we can guarantee that students from all linguistic backgrounds have an equal chance of success, which will help Nepal's educational system become more inclusive and culturally sensitive (Phyak & Sharma, 2018; García & Lin, 2017).

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